

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Austria: An Introduction

Dalilah Pichler, *KDZ Centre for Public Administration Research Austria*

The concept of people's participation in a representative democracy has many different layers. It can range from an informative character, to public consultations, and can go as far as co-decision-making or co-production. In Austria, traditional instruments of direct democracy are of high relevance, as they are embedded in the Austrian Constitution, namely the referendum, the popular initiative and the public consultation. These instruments are primarily set out for the two legislative authorities on federal and *Länder* level.¹³⁸ However, the Constitution also enables *Länder* legislation to stipulate possibilities of direct participation and involvement on municipal level, but only in matters within the municipality's own sphere of influence and reserved for citizens who are entitled to elect the municipal council. Following this proposal, all *Länder* have in different scopes embedded possibilities of local plebiscites in their legislations, which vary between the *Länder*. The main differences are of procedural nature and of how the requirements are set for the initiation of such instruments. The referendum for example is typically intended for resolutions of the local council, however citizens do not always have the possibility to enforce it. The popular initiative can be initiated in all *Länder* and in statutory cities, however not in all municipalities, depending on the provincial legislation.¹³⁹

Idealistically, the citizens of a municipality are given the right for self-governance, but the law curtails this right of direct democracy in certain topics on the local level such as questions on budget, personnel, elections, fees and taxes etc.¹⁴⁰ Public consultation is the most wide-spread and used instrument of direct democracy in Austrian municipalities.¹⁴¹ Also transparency rules and information processes for the public in municipal governments are embedded in legislation of most of the *Länder*.

Nevertheless, the legislative instruments reach to the rungs of information and consultation in the participation ladder. There is no obligation of councils or other legislative authorities to adhere to the outcome of public consultations or popular initiatives. A change would require a

¹³⁸ Alexander Balthasar, 'Die Europäische Bürgerinitiative und andere Instrumente der direkten Demokratie in Europa' in Peter Bußjäger, Alexander Balthasar and Niklas Sonntag (eds), *Direkte Demokratie im Diskurs* (New Academic Press 2014).

¹³⁹ Anna Gamper, 'Partizipation und Bürgerbeteiligung in Österreichs Städten' in Österreichischer Städtebund (ed), *Österreichs Städte in Zahlen* (2015).

¹⁴⁰ Werner Pleschberger, 'Kommunale direkte Demokratie in Österreich – Strukturelle und prozedurale Probleme und Reformvorschläge' in Theo Öhlinger and Klaus Poier (eds), *Direkte Demokratie und Parlamentarismus* (Böhlau Verlag 2015).

¹⁴¹ Thomas Prorok, 'Beteiligung von BürgerInnen in Zeiten von Open Government' in Thomas Prorok and Bernhard Krabina (eds), *Offene Stadt* (NWV 2012).

constitutional revision, as representative democracy cannot be overruled by such initiatives. This does not mean that the ‘softer forms’ of participation are not present. There have been efforts in some *Länder* to install ‘citizen councils’ of randomly chosen citizens who are representative of the population to enhance deliberation of specific political topics. These ‘citizen councils’ formulate a joint statement that serves as a suggestion for further debate and political decision-makers can derive measures from the outcome of these discussions.¹⁴² The inclusion of multiple stakeholders in planning and/or decision-making processes can also be found, often in the context of improving quality of life in a municipality. This is particularly reflected in the *Lokale Agenda 21* (LA 21) processes, based on the UN Agenda 21 action plan to which both national and *Länder* governments have committed to. With facilitation of their *Länder*, municipalities can implement different participative formats within the LA 21 process for creating a vision for the local community, the setting of common goals and strengthening cooperation between citizens, administration and politicians.

New and innovative forms of peoples’ participation have yet to come into practice. Major restrictions in the current system of municipal direct democracy are taboo topics for plebiscites and a high threshold for starting a participatory process, politicization and targeted use of such instruments for agenda setting, and the perception of participatory instruments for deliberation rather than decision-making.¹⁴³ This means that participatory mechanisms are initiated and rather driven by political parties, rather than citizen being able to actively influence public policies. Especially the referendum, where the outcome is legally binding for representatives, is rarely used although there is a general interest of the population to be more involved in direct democratic procedures.¹⁴⁴ However, the softer and less regulated forms of participation pave the way for more deliberation in the public sphere. Local governments can obtain valuable knowledge and gather ideas for certain topics, if they provide an adequate framework for the participants.

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¹⁴² Manfred Hellrigl, ‘Bürgerräte in Vorarlberg’ in Peter Bußjäger, Alexander Balthasar and Niklas Sonntag (eds), *Direkte Demokratie im Diskurs* (New Academic Press 2014).

¹⁴³ Pleschberger, ‘Kommunale direkte Demokratie in Österreich’, above.

¹⁴⁴ Max Haller and Gert Feistritzer, ‘Direkte Demokratie in Österreich. Ergebnisse einer repräsentativen Bevölkerungsumfrage’ in Peter Bußjäger, Alexander Balthasar and Niklas Sonntag (eds), *Direkte Demokratie im Diskurs* (New Academic Press 2014).

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